

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MARKETING LOGISTICS IN WHOLESALE TRADE

Bobir Ortikmirzaevich Tursunov

Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc.), Head of the Department of
Economic and Financial Security at Tashkent State University of
Economics

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5004-375X>

Kholmamatov Dior Hakberdiyevich

PhD, professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8211-9309h>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19213039>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th March 2026

Accepted: 21st March 2026

Online: 23rd March 2026

KEYWORDS

The scientific and theoretical aspects of solving marketing problems of trade enterprises, including the study of the development of marketing and logistics in wholesale trade, are reflected in the works of many foreign scientists

ABSTRACT

In the countries of the world, the USA, Japan, China and the European Union, the issues of integrated development of marketing and logistics activities in the wholesale trade system are considered one of the priority areas of scientific research. In these countries, in order to increase the competitiveness of wholesale entities, large-scale scientific research is being conducted on the development of marketing logistics models based on digital technologies, artificial intelligence and big data (Big Data) for optimizing supply chains, forecasting demand and managing inventories.

In the countries of the world, the USA, Japan, China and the European Union, the issues of integrated development of marketing and logistics activities in the wholesale trade system are considered one of the priority areas of scientific research. In these countries, in order to increase the competitiveness of wholesale entities, large-scale scientific research is being conducted on the development of marketing logistics models based on digital technologies, artificial intelligence and big data (Big Data) for optimizing supply chains, forecasting demand and managing inventories. Also, methodological approaches are being developed aimed at forming customer-oriented logistics services, improving service level assessment indicators, introducing sustainable and "green" logistics solutions, and increasing the marketing efficiency of wholesale logistics in the context of electronic and cross-border trade. This scientific research serves to expand the value chain in wholesale trade, develop logistics strategies that are flexible to market demand, and ensure sustainable competitive advantage in the global trade system.

The scientific and theoretical aspects of solving marketing problems of trade enterprises, including the study of the development of marketing and logistics in wholesale trade, are reflected in the works of many foreign scientists. In this regard, the scientific works of Carrilo R.[1], Mesa E.[2], A. Coskin Samli [3] and Adel I. El-Ansary, Hugh MacKeown [4], Kotler Ph.[5], Setiawan I., Karatajaya H. have become classics. Also, the concept of marketing logistics, its

business foundations are reflected in the scientific works of Ryszard Barcik [6], Marcin Jakubiec, M. Christopher, H. Peck, Blaik P., which indicate the formation of a modern scientific approach in the late 20th and early 19th centuries. Despite the significant contribution of these distant foreign scientists to the development of marketing and logistics in wholesale trade, the scientific methodological foundations for the development and evaluation of marketing logistics in wholesale trade have not been fully created.

In the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, such scientists as Bagiev G.L., Efimova E.A., Balabanova L.V., Germanchuk A.N., Tarzilova A.N., Karpov I.A., Sinyayeva I.M., Priplad I., S. conducted research on this issue. Although these studies covered the scientific and theoretical aspects of the development of marketing theories and logistics in wholesale trade and the development of marketing strategies in wholesale trade, methodological issues of the development of marketing logistics in wholesale trade were not studied.

Among the economists of our republic, S.S. Gulyamov [7], A.Sh. Bekmurodov, M.R. Boltabayev, M.A. Ikramov [8], A.A. Fattakhov [9,11], Sh.J. Ergashkhodzhayeva [10], M.S. Qosimova, A.N. Samadov, I.S. Khotamov, L. Abdukhalilova, B. Mamayev and others have made a great contribution to the development of the scientific and methodological foundations of marketing. It was A.A. Fattakhov, B.A. Abdukarimov [12], O.M. Pardayev [13], Tursunov B.O. [14,15] who conducted research on marketing and logistics issues in wholesale trade. However, there have been no studies on the interrelationship of marketing and logistics in wholesale trade, the integration of marketing and logistics, marketing logistics and wholesale trade as its business object. The topic of this dissertation was chosen based on these aspects.

The development of wholesale trade in the regions of Uzbekistan is closely related to economic growth and stability. Differences in trade turnover by region are due to the potential of economically centralized cities and rural areas. The volume of wholesale trade in the city of Tashkent and regions, as well as in such regions as Bukhara, Andijan and Samarkand, is high, which indicates an increase in the level of production, logistics and consumption in these regions. At the same time, trade growth rates in small regions are lower, and the lack of investment and infrastructure serves as a constraint to economic development. In turn, the expansion of wholesale trade serves to increase the production potential of enterprises, protect the domestic market from saturation, and ensure the liquidity of the republic's economy.

According to the analysis of Table 1, in 2020–2024, wholesale trade turnover in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan demonstrates a steady growth trend. The average annual growth rate by region varies from 21.2% (Surkhandarya) to 31.1% (Bukhara).

Interregional differences arise from the trade potential of economically centralized cities and rural areas. For example, Tashkent city and Tashkent region are leaders in terms of trade turnover, which make up the bulk of the republic's turnover. At the same time, regions such as Bukhara, Andijan and Samarkand have high growth rates, indicating the development of regional economic activity.

The following can be cited as the main reasons for growth:

1. Increased domestic market demand and increased incomes of the population;

2. Modernization of trade and logistics systems and improvement of transport infrastructure;

3. Economic reforms and political measures to stimulate wholesale trade;

4. Intensification of interregional competition and investment activity.

As a result, in 2024, the wholesale trade turnover in the republic will reach 456.6 trillion soums, an increase of 3.5 times compared to 2020. This confirms the growing potential of the domestic market of Uzbekistan and the positive impact of wholesale trade on economic stability.

The concept of marketing logistics began to take shape in the 1960s of the 20th century, and initially its main task was to effectively organize the process of delivering goods from the manufacturer to the consumer and reduce costs. This term was first used in scientific literature by foreign authors in 1967. In the 1970s and 1980s, scientists such as P. Tsinsyler, B. Leland, U. Harris and D. Stock focused on linking marketing and production processes with logistics, and during this period the interrelationship between marketing and logistics began to be studied.

In the 1980s and 1990s, the concept of marketing logistics further developed with the emergence of supply chain management as a strategic area of business. During this period, foreign and CIS scientists began to interpret marketing and logistics functions as a system aimed at integrating, optimizing resource flows and satisfying customer needs. Since the 1990s, marketing logistics has been widely used as a concept that includes not only the delivery of products from the manufacturer to the consumer, but also the effective management of the supply chain and material resources.

Thus, the marketing and logistics systems work in harmony, forming the concept of marketing logistics. This concept requires the establishment of a process-based management system in the enterprise. That is, while in traditional marketing logistics logistics is considered a separate functional department, attention is focused on the transition from functions to processes, that is, on managing the chain of creating value for the consumer.

The concept of marketing logistics requires the introduction of modern management approaches in the enterprise management system. Now the main attention should be paid not to traditional functional departments, but to the integrated management of the chain of creating added value for the consumer. In this case, through the integration of marketing and logistics systems, the efficiency of the enterprise's activities increases, and the ability to quickly respond to market demands arises. Improving the business processes of marketing logistics not only increases the efficiency of internal management, but also increases the market flexibility of the enterprise. By creating an integrated marketing-logistics system, it is possible to reduce costs, increase the speed of service, achieve competitive advantage, and flexibly respond to consumer needs.

Marketing and logistics integration is of strategic importance in increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of wholesale trade. To this end, it is recommended to implement the following measures:

1. Coordination of marketing strategy and flow management. Wholesale trade enterprises should develop a mechanism for combining marketing strategy with management

of material and information flows. This will allow determining market demand, forecasting customer needs and optimizing the flow of goods.

2. Adapting the distribution system to the consumer. It is necessary to adapt goods to the demands and needs of end consumers through distribution and logistics systems. As a result, not only consumer satisfaction will increase, but also the operational efficiency of wholesale trade enterprises will be ensured.

3. Establishment of wholesale distribution centers. It is recommended to establish wholesale distribution centers in free economic zones, small industrial zones and large industrial regions of Uzbekistan. In these centers, wholesale trade organizations will have the opportunity to effectively use resources by jointly implementing marketing and logistics functions.

4. Optimization of distribution centers and warehouses. Wholesale costs can be reduced by introducing modern logistics methods for transporting, storing and managing products. At the same time, placing centers in geographically optimal locations increases delivery efficiency.

5. Development of business cooperation in the “manufacturer - wholesale - retail” chain. Creating seamless integration between all participants in the wholesale chain serves to harmonize marketing and logistics processes, manage commodity flows quickly and efficiently, and also meet consumer demand at a high level.

6. Creation of a business process model of marketing logistics. Wholesale enterprises should develop an integrated business process model of marketing logistics in order to achieve competitive advantage. This model combines marketing functions (market research, pricing and assortment policy, sales promotion) and logistics functions (inventory management, transportation, warehousing, delivery).

Thus, the integration of marketing and logistics is a key strategic tool in wholesale trade to increase competitiveness, optimize costs, and provide high quality service to consumers. By implementing a modern marketing-logistics concept, wholesale enterprises achieve long-term sustainable development and increased profits.

References:

1. Carrilo R. Trade marketing/R.Carrillo. – Lima, Junio del, del, 2017. – 79 p.,
2. Mesa E. Trade Marketing/E.Mesa//Universidad De San Buenaventura. – Colombia. Bogotá D.C., 2014. – 28 p.,
3. A.Coskin Samli & Adel I.El-Ansary (2007). The role of wholesalers in developing countries. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research Journal, vol. 17, pp. 353-358,
4. Hugh MacKeown (2007) Wholesaling and wholesaling research: A practitioner's viewpoint. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research Journal, vol. 17, pp. 413-422,
5. Kotler Ph., Setiawan I., Kartajaya H. Marketing 3.0: From Products to Customers to the Human Spirit. – wiley, 2012.
6. Ryszard Barcik, Marcin Jakubiec (2013). Marketing logistics. <https://docplayer.net/4272544-Marketing-logistics-bielsko-biala-poland-email-rbarcik-ath-bielsko-pl-bielsko-biala-poland-email-m-jakubiec-ath-bielsko-pl.html>, Martin Christopher and

- Helen Peck. Marketing Logistics. Second edition. 2003. 172 Pages, BLAIK, P., 2001: Logistyka. Koncepcja zintegrowanego zarządzania, wyd. II, PWE, Warszawa.
- 7.Gulyamov S.S., Jumayev N.Kh., Rakhmanov D.A., Toshkhodjayev M.M. Efficiency of investments in the social sphere. – T.: Economics, 2019;
- 8.Ikramov M.A., Pardayev M.K., Abdukhalilova L.T. Statistical analysis in marketing research. – T.: Sano-standart, 2022;
- 9.Fattakhov A.A., Anufriyev A.I. Marketing and logistic technologies in commercial business. – T.: Economics world, 2019;
- 10.Ergashkhodjaeva Sh.D., Samadov A.N., Sharipov I.B. Marketing. – T.: Economics, 2013
- 11.A.A.Fattakhov. Marketing strategy in wholesale trade and ways to increase its effectiveness. Abstract of the dissertation written for the degree of Doctor of Economics. Tashkent, 2006.- 46 p.,
- 12.Abdukarimov B.A. Economics of domestic trade. Textbook, in 2 parts – T.: "Science and Technology". 2015. – 387 p.,
- 13.Pardaev O.M. Improving organizational and economic mechanisms for increasing the efficiency of product storage and sales services. Abstract of doctoral dissertation. Samarkand, 2017, - 90 p.
- 14.Ortikmirzaevich, T. B. (2017). Improving logistics as main factor in textile capacity usage. Zbornik radova Departmana za geografiju, turizam i hotelijerstvo, 46(2), 44-52.
- 15.Tursunov, B. (2017). Role of Managing Industrial Stocks in Increasing of Textile Enterprises Capacity. Journal of Applied Management and Investments, 6(4), 260-266.

